

FROM CATSTROPHE TO RESILIENCE

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Abstract

How do we cope with catastrophe events using existing models? Are we going a step forward and focus on sustainable solutions taking into account a more holistic approach and resilience concept? Natural disasters are characterized by different patterns in recent years. Urban communities have developed assets too vulnerable to disasters and now they are about to have high damage. There is a need for a new framework that takes into consideration models, crisis management, new holistic concepts along with social components. The concept of resilience to natural disasters, preferably resilience to floods will be the main subject of this paper.

1 INTRODUCTION

As a major adverse event, resulting from natural processes, e.g. floods present a natural disaster. Measuring the number of disasters per type for the period from 1998 to 2017, floods have more than 43.4% and 3143 event in total (EM-DAT). Commonly used term disaster and catastrophe draw attention to its meaning. The disaster is caused by hazards (natural or technological) while catastrophe is a disaster with tragic outcome of a personal or public situation. In general these two terms are used equally, so in the paper, the disaster will be the adopted term.

Analysing the different concepts related to risks focusing on how to manage pre and post event, what actions to take into account?

Disasters become more complex nowadays. The impacts that disasters pose to society along with existing fragility and vulnerability of people and built environment are bigger. Reducing disaster risks, Disaster Risk Reduction approaches propose systematic analysis of hazard reduction, lessened vulnerability of people and built environment, and control exposure. Paper analyses components of disaster risk management and resilience as one of the key concept. How the resilience is seen and how the methodology is developed to be applicable to urban systems taking into accounts both local community and built environment. The method is applied on nine case studies and the results are comparable focusing on different dimensions.

2 DISASTER RISK MANAGEMENT

By managing disasters the understanding is the key: what are the components of the risk, the drivers of the risk and key concepts.

Floods in urban systems cause disruption on many levels of functioning and ask for fast reaction. With disaster, especially in urban areas into the play comes a risk. It is often recognized as a consequence of interaction between three main elements: hazard, vulnerability and exposure. It is very important to highlight that all three elements need to be into play in order to have risk.

Natural events (here we are focused on floods) are hazards when they have potential to threaten people and urban systems. Hazards are creating disasters. Clarity about disaster classification is crucial. Classification is therefore proposed to disaggregate groups, types and sub-types. Clearly, the analysis becomes more precise and provides better focus on particular disaster. There are two generic disaster groups: natural and technological. Floods, as natural disaster, are listed as main type of hydrological hazards (Below R, et al., 2010). The disaster sub-types are listed with respect to different flood types. As one of focal point in this paper, floods that occur nowadays differ to its patterns, mainly duration and frequency.

Exposure element comes into play when people, infrastructure, tangible assets are in hazard prone area. If there is no exposure in flood prone area, there is no risk.

The extent to which exposed people and economic assets are at risk is generally determined how vulnerable they are. Drivers for exposure is concentration of people and assets usually in cities. This is driven by rapid urbanization, population growth and economic development. Hazard prone areas such as coastal or riparian areas are often places with high concentration of people and tangible assets. This is increasing risk to dangerous levels.

Vulnerability presents a pre-event characteristic of a system that has a potential to harm. Vulnerability is in a function of exposure or sensitivity of a system to disturbance. This is explained through answer on question who or what is at risk? Vulnerability defines the conditions determined with physical, social, economic, or environmental factors or processes which are increasing the weakness of community to the impact of hazard (UN/ISDR, 2004). Specific definition of vulnerability to flood events is given in Balica (2013) as the extent to which a system is susceptible to floods due to exposure, a perturbation, in conjunction with its ability (or inability) to cope, recover, or basically adapt. Vulnerability is a human dimension of disasters and it the result of the range of the economic, social, cultural, institutional, political and psychological factors that shape people lives and the environment that they are (Twigg, 2004).

Vulnerability is very complex and relates to different factors: physical, social, economical and environmental. It is also depending on cultural, political, institutional, natural dimension, everything that is creating their living environment.

There are many risk drivers. The common one is climate change, environmental degradation, economic development, existing poverty and inequality and non proper governance. There are many ways how climate change is increasing disaster risk. By increasing global temperature the agricultural sector is directly hit. The sea level rise is dictating increase hazards in low land areas. Also, change in geographic distribution of weather related hazards. Decreasing in resilience is also triggered by climate change and directly hits the poorer communities and developing countries.

Ecological degradation is both driver for disaster risk and its consequence. It is occurring when environment is not able to meet social and ecological needs. Weak governance stands as one key driver for disaster risk. This element is often linked with other risk drivers such as poverty, poor planned urban development and globalized economic development.

The key concepts of disaster risk are defined through: capacity, deterministic and probabilistic risk, losses (both direct and indirect), disaster risk reduction and risk management and resilience. Capacity refers to all strengths attributes and resources available within the community, organization to manage reduce disaster risk and increase resilience. Within the concept of deterministic and probabilistic risk the analysis is focused on single or multiple scenarios. Probabilistic risk is simulating future disasters based on scientific evidence. These risk assessment as a result is solving the problem posed by the limits of historical data. The deterministic risk models are treating the event as finite. Within this approach the scenarios are modelled with known input values and out values are observed.

Disaster risk management focuses on managing risk not disaster. Focusing on multi sector approach, people-centred, building resilience, increasing capacity, creating the culture of prevention and resilience the disaster risk management includes the huge palette of strategies. The available strategies

are focused on avoidance and construction of new risks, addressing risks. The effective disaster risk reduction is combination of top-down institutional changes and strategies and bottom-up local and community based approaches.

3 RESILIENCE FRAMEWORK

Resilience is a one of the main concepts of disaster risks. As a term, is often left open to debate and doesn't have a general or consensual definition although it is increasingly used in integrated urban drainage management, (Ashley *et al.*, 2012; De Bruijn 2004; Klein *et al.*, 1998; Sayers *et al.*, 2003; Sendzimir *et al.*, 2007; Vis *et al.*, 2003;). The diverse interpretations of resilience reflect the complexity of this concept and made it 'difficult' in implementation of integrated urban drainage management. From a general perspective, resilience represents the capacity of an urban system or community exposed to hazard to adapt by resisting or changing in order to reach an acceptable level of functioning, organization and structure (UN/ISDR, 2004).

By narrowing down the resilience the specified resilience comes to focus. This resilience deals with following principle: "of what to what" (Carpenter *et al.*, 2001). It can be defined by identifying what system attributes are to be resilient, and to what kind of disturbances. Specified resilience in the context of Integrated Urban Drainage Management (IUDM) has often been defined in a restricted sense to express the ability of the whole system to recover from the reaction of flood waves (Klein *et al.*, 1998; Sayers *et al.*, 2003; De Bruijn, 2004). Suitable definition for resilience adopted for the research in this paper is proposed by the United Nations' International Strategy for Disaster Reduction (UNISDR). In the context of urban flooding, resilience can be defined as follows:

"Resilience is the capacity of a system, community or society potentially exposed to hazards to adapt, by resisting or changing in order to reach and maintain an acceptable level of functioning and structure. This is determined by the degree to which the social system is capable of organising itself to increase this capacity for learning from past disasters for better future protection and to improve risk reduction measures" (UN/ISDR, 2004).

From this wide sense the concept provides a perhaps more suitable background framework to develop and assess integrated approaches to flood risk management. Resilience is therefore specified here in respect to the broader social-ecological context as the capacity of the system to absorb flood waves in annual variability, and to reorganize while undergoing change in flood wave frequency and severity in the long term, so as to enable it to function normally. The resilience approach is aiming to prevent the urban system to move from an undesirable state from which it is not possible to recover from flood impact to functional state. These preventions go in following directions (

Figure 1):

1. Adjusting the thresholds of a system with respect to changes in response to flood waves;
2. Defining the level to which system is capable of self organizing;
3. Define the level to which the system is able to build and increase capacity for learning and adaptation.

This defines resilience thinking, a different point of view for guiding and organizing urban systems.

Figure 1: Carrying capacity, vulnerability and resilience

Defined terminology of vulnerability and resilience stands as an important element in the analysis of urban areas and their existing flood risks but there should be a distinction between the flood vulnerability and resilience of people on one side and the urban structure on the other side.

The resilient urban systems and urban communities should have ability to accept, resist, recover and learn from the events. Capacity of urban systems and communities is improved in each part of the flood risk management cycle. It covers actions related to preparedness, response and recovery. Within this research the five elements of flood risk management are developed: Reflect, Relief, Resist, Response, and Recovery. These new elements explain as follow:

Figure 2: Defined elements for flood risk management cycle with transition to resilience concept - 5R concept (Batica, 2013)

Relief phase – Defined as 'a buffer' where existing structures and urban functions accept floodwater (green areas, different playgrounds, etc) using its own capacities. Implementation of physical, technical, non-structural and procedural measures relates to the concept “living with floods”.

Resist phase – Reduction of flood risk if possible. This is in direct connection with existing threshold capacity. Under this phase, the activities rely on the existing structural (done before flood event). Limiting flood damage and easing recovery by planning and building adaptation, infrastructure, surfaces and economic activity relate to the concept of resistance.

Response phase – Focus is on measures taken during the flood related to crisis management. At this time, flood impact is reduced by implementation of physical, technical, non-structural and procedural measures relates to the concept “living with floods”.

Recovery phase – Take into account activities that provide support by developing capacity building in communities enable to cope with the impacts after flooding events, cleaning and rebuilding.

Reflect phase – Here, the focus is on increasing awareness and adaptive capacity, learning from past event and/or preparation for an uncertain future. These activities enhance awareness and engagement in all aspects of flood risk. It is influencing the managing at the policy level (politicians/decision makers), professionals (of the involved authorities and elsewhere) and at the public participation (people, companies, developers, insurance companies).

Presented elements introduce resilience concept into flood risk management cycle. The elements are structured into different phases starting from striking the flood through whole duration of event including post flood period. The last element is very important since it focuses on: learning from event, rising awareness, alerting and engaging decision makers and key stakeholders.

3.1 Flood Resilience Assessment

Assessment focuses on analysis of urban system. The system components are mapped with respect to different function in the system. Also the system is scaled into: parcel, block, district and city (the whole system). The methodology focuses on mapping the components of urban system for improving analysis and focus on critical elements. Mapping of urban system is needed in order to achieve a balanced study of flood resilience. In addition, scaling of urban system allows being able to recognize

main urban patterns. Mapping and scaling of urban system breaks down the structure of urban pattern into physical components and system requirements (Daniell, K.A. Et al, 2005). Functional analysis of system will allow evaluating flood resilience of each system element.

Physical components of the systems are urban functions and services: buildings, streets, parks, water distribution network, shops, industrial buildings, electricity network, religion areas, etc. Some of them represent assets that the city needs to have in order to perform while others provide connections between different system components. Urban functions of a city define physical components that urban system needs to provide as fundamental needs to residents. The physical component of a city has spatial extension and the expression is through units (m²). There are nine main urban functions, which urban system needs to have in order to fulfil requirements related to integral need provided to residents. The urban functions are listed as follows:

- houses (individual or collective),
- educational areas (for local and non-local education services),
- food (area for food storage),
- work areas (areas for industry and areas for non-industrial activities),
- areas established for location of police, fire brigade and rescue services (on local level), health areas (hospitals on local and non-local level),
- areas for leisure and tourism (on local and non-local level) and
- areas for religion activities (churches and cemeteries).

The city services give connectivity between physical components. Services in the city gives functionality to urban features (e.g. the function of a house is to provide space for living).

Figure 3: Mapping of the city according to urban functions and services

3.2 Flood Resilience Index (FRI)

The need for index introduction comes from the intent to have a compact presentation of resilience. The index is represented by number and describes the **level of flood resilience in analysed area and for certain flood characteristics with value from 0 to 5**.

This way of presentation comes from considering resilience as a characteristic by definition and represents **ability to accept** a disturbance up to some level. This ability is defined up to the level where the system is able to organize itself and preserve the structure and function. Reflected in urban systems this means that resilience is defined up to the level that urban structure and urban community are able to accept disturbance, preserve the 'level of functioning', organize and recover from it.

To measure flood resilience in urban spaces, the index takes into account several indicators based on the notions of the five R's of resilience regarding flood management: Reflect, Relief, Resist, Response, and Recovery.

There is a different process of index evaluation based on scale dependency. For the small scales: (i) parcel/building and (ii) block scale, index evaluation focuses on the urban function. In the process of calculating the FRI, external and internal requirements are evaluated. The method for macro scale: (i) district and (ii) city scale takes into account whole system through five dimensions.

Figure 4: FRI diagram assessment for the different scales

3.2.1 Micro scale assessment

The evaluation on micro scale takes into account urban functions and services as main elements. The evaluation of FRI for property scale where focus is on urban function and its structure and level of functioning during flooding conditions presents a union of all external and internal requirements presented in table below. Each mapped property is evaluated and presented with flood resilience level.

Table 1: FRI evaluation at property scale

Requirements for urban function	Availability level (0-5)	FRI (property scale)
EXTERNAL SERVICES (r_e)	0,1,2,3,4,5	$FRI_{building} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^5 r_{ei} \times w_i + \sum_{i=1}^3 r_{ii} \times w_i}{8}$
Energy	0,1,2,3,4,5	
Water	0,1,2,3,4,5	
Waste	0,1,2,3,4,5	
Communication	0,1,2,3,4,5	
Transport	0,1,2,3,4,5	
INTERNAL SERVICES (r_i)		
Food availability	0,1,2,3,4,5	
Occupation of urban function	0,1,2,3,4,5	
Access to urban function	0,1,2,3,4,5	
Where:		
r_e is an external service		
r_i is an internal service		
w_i is assigned weight		

3.2.2 Macro scale assessment

The assessment of Flood Resilience Index on the parcel and block scale is focused on the building (urban function) while for the bigger scale (city/district) the evaluation of Flood Resilience Index is done through five dimensions (natural, physical, economical, social and institutional). These five dimensions describe the physical and social attributes of urban system. One of the main objective criteria was to evaluate urban community and its ability to accept certain disturbance and recover from it. The scheme on Figure 5 presents the flow path for evaluation of FRI for macro scale. The calculation is done using the developed matrix with 91 indicators that are corresponding to different

element of flood risk management cycle following already developed 5R concept. Evaluation continues with allocation each indicator to particular dimension (natural, physical, economic, social and institutional).

Figure 5: Schematic presentation of FRI evaluation of city/district scale

The overall resilience assessment is developed to fit the urban systems and provide better guidance to disaster risk reduction. The methodology is developed for flood hazard and takes into account different scales and different levels of data.

Figure 6: Schematic presentation of FRI evaluation of city/district scale

4 EXAMPLES

In this section the results from different case studies will be presented. In eight years log period, method has been applied on nine cases study areas located in Europe and Asia. Focusing on macro scales the results are eligible for comparison and analysis. They offer key stakeholders the perspective on natural, physical, institutional, economical, and social dimensions. This scale is chosen because of data availability.

Table 2: Case studies with calculated FRI for macro scales

Case study	Country	Dimensions					FRI
		Natural	Social	Economic	Institutional	Physical	
Ayutthaya	Thailand	3.00	2.76	3.57	1.75	3.44	2.90

Barcelona	Spain	3.50	3.25	3.81	3.31	3.62	3.49
Beijing	China	2.50	2.55	3.00	1.83	2.72	2.52
Chatellailon-Plage	France	2.50	3.65	3.29	3.62	2.12	3.04
Genoa	Italy	1.88	3.39	2.38	2.00	1.76	2.28
Hamburg	Germany	4.00	3.87	3.96	3.71	4.20	3.95
Nice	France	3.50	3.17	3.65	3.70	3.25	3.45
Taipei	Taiwan	3.50	3.36	1.70	3.61	3.06	3.05

Figure 7: Radar chart presentation of FRI values for nine case studies

Figure above shows the FRI values calculated for different dimensions. The values show the level of flood resilience in dimensions based on case study analysis. The calculation is done using developed matrix with 91 indicators that were evaluated for particular case study taking into account natural, social, economic, institutional and physical settings.

Presented tool is practical for different stakeholders where they have a possibility to 'play' with the different indicators exploring how to increase resilience. Also, there is a possibility to create different scenarios with different strategies and make comparison.

5 CONCLUSIONS

The Flood Resilience Index (FRI) represents a tool for stakeholders and decision makers. The concept brings a new philosophy to urban systems, 'living with floods'. Presented approach transforms the existing structure of urban system and creates a system that is accepting the water with minimal damages, system that is able to recover in a minimum time frame and system that is able to have a certain level of functioning during the flood. The resilience of a system could be improved by using diverse regulations such as institutional, urban planning and design, architectural design, public participation, financial stimulation, etc. The importance is in the possibility to use experience from flood resilience urban systems and avoid huge flood damages and dysfunction. The developing urban systems can find a good practice and good paths towards flood resiliency without reaching a low level of functioning.

As presented the framework is applicable on different institutional setting in different urban systems. Future development of presented methodology focuses on application to different hazards such as fire,

landslides, droughts as well as technological risk. The framework is potentially applicable to any urban system on any geographic scale. Connections and dependences between main city elements and natural hazards (in this case urban flooding process) have to be defined. With its implementation, social, economical, political and cultural relations within city will be more visible and better established.

The approach should uncover the role of physical components of urban system and population in relation to urban flooding processes. A further strategy focuses on simulation of community losses and recovery measures. As a major challenge that faces urban systems nowadays, the research on resilience prioritizes in following years.

6 NOMENCLATURE

FRI - Flood Resilience Index

DRR - Disaster Risk reduction

UNISDR - United Nations' International Strategy for Disaster Reduction

EM-DAT - International Disaster Data Base

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